

laser → slit 1 → cleanup → slit 2 → mass channel → measurement plane

SCHEMATIC PROFILE OF AN OPTICAL MASS CHANNEL

staged beam-conditioning pipeline:

- 1.laser source
- 2.primary 0.1 mm diffraction slit (initial conditioning)
- 3.secondary ~1-2 mm clipping/cleanup aperture
- 4.final 0.1 mm diffraction slit
- 5.downstream mass-channel interaction region

Isolated DC power supply

All inner surfaces of the Mass Density Cubes are painted with optically absorbent paint

All inner surfaces of the Mass Density Cubes are spot checked to optically absorbent 95%-97%

Surfaces and edges are visually inspected after light sanding (3000 grit) for any obvious imperfections at 10x magnification

Five Mass-Channel Assemblies per set, leveled with each other with .02mm shims as needed

Four sets, Five samples per set - each leveled together for batch testing. Level to $\pm .05$ mm

Conducted in an underground basement 12 ft below ground with no ventilation and temperature stable to $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{F}$ over two weeks. Short ~3-minute test runs per set/distance, heavy wooden table, insulating LEGO structure, and baseline images taken before, during, and after each set/distance minimized thermal drift, vibration, and alignment